

MORPHOLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS OF TUBERCULOSIS IN THE SPINE POST-COVID-19

Mamazhonov I.M.

Makhkamov N.J.

Andizhan State Medical Institute, Andizhan

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Significance: After the COVID-19 pandemic, structural and functional changes in the spine, chest, and lumbar regions are formed, resulting in the thinning of the bone and lumbar disc as a result of degenerative changes over time, and such cases require early detection of the etiology of various diseases, especially tuberculosis.

Purpose: to study the effectiveness of histological examination in determining the changes in the bone tissue and fibrotic ring of the vertebral disc with tuberculosis etiology in the spine under the influence of Covid-19.

Material and examination methods: Post-examination biopsy of tuberculous spondylitis and disc herniation in the hospitals of Andijan State Medical Institute in order to study the topography and morphology of degenerative and dystrophic changes in the thoracic and lumbar regions of the spine after Covid-19 and in the autopsy department of the Republican Pathological Anatomy Center of the UzR SSV 30 we used the materials obtained in the surgical practice of tuberculous spondylitis in patients aged up to 65 years.

Results of the study and their discussion: The selection of the obtained materials in different age group was studied the changes of the bone tissue of the spine and the fibrotic ring of the lumbar disc under the influence of Covid-19. Changes in the structure of the vertebral body bone tissue and intervertebral disc after shocks and various loads, i.e., a violation of its elasticity, leads to the thinning of the fibrous ring and its rupture. In patients, if the load begins to increase, the bone body and the vertebral disc are deformed. In this process, the tissues of the vibrating nucleus are displaced, the inner surface of the fibroid is densely attached to it, and it is damaged. When studying the morpho functional state of the fibrous structures in the fibrotic subcutaneous tissue, it was found that the fibrous structures in the tissue were manifested at different levels due to strong dystrophic and destructive changes in them, and the fibrous structures in these areas were combined with each other, forming a homogeneous coarse protein substance. it is observed that he did. It should be mentioned that in addition to these pathomorphological changes, calcinosis develops in some

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areas of the tissue. As a result, sequestered hard and disc fragments must be completely surgically removed, especially sequestered fragments (including the rare ones that penetrate the subarachnoid space). determined that pathomorphological changes should be determined based on individual approach to age, lifestyle and work activities.

Conclusion: The results of the conducted scientific research showed that histological examination provides not only early diagnosis, but also early surgical intervention in studying the disease levels of patients and making a correct diagnosis.

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